

TRAINING OF PEDAGOGICAL PERSONNEL TASHKENT-THE BASICS OF
METHODS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7583349>

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Foundation of Advanced Research Publishers

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Abstract: The article considers the organizational and methodological aspects of preparation for teaching at the university, in particular, professional competencies specified in the qualification requirements of areas, types of lectures used in the development of theoretical knowledge, practical foundations for preparing for teaching.

Keywords: pedagogical activity, professional competence, qualification requirements, types of lectures, practical exercises.

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Received: 22-01-2023

Accepted: 22-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

Decree No. 4623 "on measures for the further development of the field of pedagogical education" of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the task "to identify young people with high interest in the pedagogical profession and to introduce a continuous system of their targeted training and upbringing" [1].

The implementation of these tasks necessitates the revision and updating of the content, form and methods of preparing university students for pedagogical activity on a scientific basis.

Preparation for pedagogical activity is prepared on the basis of qualification requirements, training plans and programs developed for each direction of The Bachelor's degree. The content of preparation for pedagogical activity in qualification students is carried out with the subjects of study "general pedagogy", "general psychology", "methods of teaching specialist disciplines" and qualifying pedagogical practice. It is also established that students in general pedagogy theory, methods, tools and technologies of Education, general and private methods, pedagogical technologies, management of the educational system and pedagogical skills will receive professional competencies in the qualification requirements [2].

Lecture classes are considered a form of education aimed at acquiring theoretical knowledge in the preparation for pedagogical activity and are organized on the basis of the formula "from pedagogical theory - to pedagogical practice". Problematic lecture, lecture-conference, video-lecture and Multimedia in achieving quality and efficiency in the process of preparation for pedagogical activity lecture types are used. Of course, it will be necessary to take into account such factors as the purpose, content, volume, level of study of the topic of the lecture, as well as

the capabilities, interests of students. At the same time, the lecture will need to create conditions close to pedagogical practice, bring and solve situations that form important professional qualities into the process of acquiring theoretical knowledge.

From the creation of a plan of lecture topics on the subject of " general pedagogy " to the transfer of rules, concepts and information in each plan, it is necessary to organize and implement it, referring to the competencies presented precisely in the qualification requirements. In particular, on the topic " organizational forms and methods of education " it is important not only to give a classification of organizational forms or techniques of education, to explain their specifics, but also to focus on what organizational forms and methods of education are selected on the basis of. For example, it is necessary to cite the fact that methods depend on the nature of the subject, the size of the educational material, the time of training (for example, 45 minutes), the relationship between the teacher and students, the material and technical support of the audience and several other factors .

It is also necessary to explain what is the relationship of principles with the laws of education when revealing the content of educational principles, and to convey the rules arising from each principle, that is, the aspects that the teacher must follow in the educational process, through handouts. For example, when implementing the principle of mindfulness and activity, the following rules should be implemented: a clear understanding of the purpose of the educational material by the student is a prerequisite for a conscious assimilation of the subject, what is the student?, why? and how? let him understand that you need to do, logic every word, sentence, concept to ensure their complete understanding on the basis of, explain with specific life examples, eliminate distracting factors from the object being studied (fiddling, being late for Class, breaking discipline), teach independent thinking, etc.

And in the principle of exhibitionism, it is necessary to apply not only through illustration, but also in the creation of a problem situation, to prepare an exhibition together with readers, to use modern means, to build attention, observation, a culture of thinking in students through support. At the same time, it will be necessary not to abuse visual means, but rather to create conditions for abstract thinking.

In the principle of systematicity, it is necessary to explain the educational material in sequence into logically completed parts, pay attention to pronunciation, pay attention to the mastery of knowledge, skills, competencies in the lesson. On the principle of intelligibility, it is necessary to teach, relying on the capabilities of students, the level of development, it will be necessary to correctly select the pace,

pace of the educational process, use methods of comparison, comparison, as well as emphasize that the teacher's speech is the basis of this principle.

It is necessary to pay attention to the use of the latest achievements of pedagogy and psychology, pedagogical technologies in the principle of science, ensuring a legal connection between science and the subject of study, revealing the relevant aspects of technology, culture news to the topic, explaining the linguistic meaning and of course the content of terms, ensuring that the information provided is

And in the principle of the unity of theory and practice, to mean that each subject is a vital necessity, science is based on a practical need lighting its development, forming a conscious and positive attitude to work, talking about new technologies, etc. The above principles contribute to the individualization of the educational process, the formation of knowledge and qualifications, norms of social morality, the formation of pedagogical influence and the formation of professional competence in students, taking into account such psychological characteristics of a person as his personality, that is, his memory, will, ability, temperament, character, life purpose, specific acceptance.

In modern conditions, the preparation of students for pedagogical activity is carried out not only by a thorough acquisition of theoretical knowledge in lecture sessions, but also by applying several types of practical classes and completing the corresponding tasks. Especially based on the nature, size and level of the subject, the practical training Turin's correct selection determines the effectiveness of the preparation process for pedagogical Activity [3].

In the discipline" general pedagogy " the following types of practical classes are used: independent work, applied research, educational discussion, group seminar training, problem case solving and educational training. Practical classes form in students the skill of applying theoretical knowledge in practice, provide an opportunity to actively apply research techniques, compare, observe, analyze, draw conclusions and conduct independent research. At the same time, practical classes expand the possibilities of students to find effective solutions to various situations in the pedagogical process of tactile thinking. The most important serve to form professional competence and Professional Responsibility.

In conclusion, it can be said that preparing students for pedagogical activity in higher education is a complex and multifaceted process. The successful and effective result of this process is associated with the correct choice of the optimal method, means and forms of the educational process of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and abilities.

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